

МАТЕРІАЛИ ДОПОВІДЕЙ ТА ВИСТУПІВ УЧАСНИКІВ КОНФЕРЕНЦІЇ

СЕКЦІЯ 1: СОЦІАЛЬНІ ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЇ ТА ВИКЛИКИ ВІЙНИ

Kozhukhalova Alisa¹

Email: alice232305@gmail.com

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20303838>

Sociology and Contemporary Social Transformations: Proceedings of the 18th All-Ukrainian Conference of students and young scientists with international participation (Kyiv, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, November 10-11, 2025). – Kyiv: Naukova Stolytsia, 2026. – 129 p.

The fall, transformation and rise of international security, the cascade of wars and Ukraine's key role in shaping and changing the system of security altogether

The modern concept of international security began to develop as new nation-states emerged from the collapsed empires and had to establish policies to protect themselves. There are a lot of theories to support this claim. Charles Tilly, for example, has introduced the bellicist theory of state formation, which can be summed up by quoting Tilly himself – «War made the State, and the State made War». This is where I'd like to delve deeper into the topic of wars and their consequences, which not only make a state (or weaken a state) but also create something greater...

In this new modern world that we live in, wars create systems of peace and safety, which may be broken and again created. Mainly, we can come to a conclusion that cascade of wars (also called «cascades of violence», «conflict cascade») makes a path to this creation. For example, the Yalta Conference, 1945, shaped a postwar peace that represented a collective security order.

The evolution of the nation-states, through today's perspective, can be categorized in different phases. The first is considered to have occurred during the time between the French Revolution and World War I, when nation states emerged due to the influence of the ideas of the French Revolution. Afterwards, World War I and World War II brought the emergence of hundreds of new states in Europe. Resulting in the enlargement of the nation states formed in the nineteenth century, in terms of population and territory. The third wave, which can also be described as the anti-colonial movement, occurred during the Cold War era. Finally, the fourth wave, which started soon after the end of the Cold War, and is considered to still be ongoing.

Obviously, the emergence of new nation-states calls for guarantees of their safety. Given that, international security occurs as a subfield of international

¹Bachelor's student, Political Science, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv

relations. Security has been inextricably linked to the military aspect, as most countries seek to maximize their military power to ensure their security and survival against all perceived threats, including attempts to subordinate their existence to another state, terrorist organization or other armed group. In the twenty-first century, international security took on new forms. The notion of international security as security between states belongs to the twentieth century. Threats no longer come primarily from states. As Kivalova & Cherniavskiy (2024) mention, the threats come from ethnic groups obsessed with hyper-nationalism, from criminal gangs, mafia rule, from epidemics, AIDS, terrorism, unsafe food, from poverty, from poor economic management, from overpopulation, from failed states, from refugee flows and, most importantly, from pollution and the consequences of pollution, irrigation and the destruction of nature, as well as the diversification of nature.

This marks the exceptional need for global cooperation and consolidation which has a greater goal in mind that is a shared need to fight for the peace and stability on the globe. That being – international security systems, which serve as measures of protection and preventive mechanisms as well as defense.

However, the vulnerability of those systems and their malfunctions have been proven with very bloody examples. World War II and the already mentioned Yalta Conference resulted in emergence of the UN Security Council. The Council's goal of maintaining international peace and security by a number of necessary mechanisms was proven ineffective, unfortunately. Why? Because it surely didn't stop a permanent member of the UN Security Council from committing war crimes in the neighboring country. This being said, it is without a doubt a clear malfunction of the system, which was overlooked given the lack of such threats or past experiences. It is also clear that such a drastic event reveals the vulnerability of the system, which could have not been predicted before they have occurred, and calls for a new one which can promise a stable and safe future.

Sometimes, the system may not «fall» or malfunction but simply not be applicable. Given new threats, the field transforms in accordance with those new threats. An example of that would be cyberattacks. New threats require new methods of defense, which causes the system to transform. The effectiveness of security guarantees can be limited by a variety of factors, including the political will of guarantor states, limitations in international law and other factors. The tragic terrorist 9/11 attack, has transformed the security system and introduced a number of new measures applied across different countries and created a system of cooperation between them, which was new, yet somehow it became effective and showed results.

As you could've already imagined, every war that happens doesn't really change the system drastically, sure it may make it better and more efficient, but it doesn't necessarily call for a completely new one. However, sometimes the system can be ruined by the violation of previously set rules. The system has failed again, as mentioned briefly above, and unfortunately drastically. The price to pay was and still is the lives of Ukrainians.

If it is unclear how Ukraine plays a key role in the future of international security, it is as follows. Ukrainians have gained many unique experiences, first-

hand knowledge in many fields as well as the most practiced, ability to self-organize. Examples of that would be the volunteering groups operating for more than 11 years, homeland defense organization that were organized by the initiative of civilians, medics who had many sleepless nights after night attacks, and other services that worked and were on high alert in the bleak of night. The abovementioned phenomena are something that made Ukrainians unique and more stronger than ever before. Moreover, National Institute for Strategic Studies in their 2025 report «Society Transformed by War» state: «Most Ukrainians do not feel hostility or alienation toward compatriots with different opinions or lifestyles. Ukrainian society continues to demonstrate tolerance and pluralism, even on issues directly tied to national security. Meanwhile, the assumption that Ukrainian society is polarized, particularly regarding worldview and group relations, remains widespread but is unsupported by evidence. According to experts, no real internal fault lines exist that could lead to the fragmentation of Ukrainian society» (Society Transformed by War, 2025).

Ukraine has most definitely earned its place at a table where decisions are being made, and its hardworking and incredibly consolidated society has yet again proved its worth not only to itself but also to the whole globe. Those lived experiences of millions of Ukrainians are priceless. They will surely lead to a brighter future, and Ukrainian society will and should be active and present in future decision-making regarding global peace.

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